

MODELING MONO AND MULTI-REPOSITORY DILEMMA FOR MICROSERVICE SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE DEVELOPMENT

RADOVAN ČIKIĆ¹, MILOŠ MILIĆ², SINIŠA VLAJIĆ³

¹ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Organizational Sciences, Belgrade, cikicsm@gmail.com, 0009-0005-2069-7022

² University of Belgrade, Faculty of Organizational Sciences, Belgrade, milos.milic@fon.bg.ac.rs, 0000-0002-2521-7607

³ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Organizational Sciences, Belgrade, sinisa.vlajic@fon.bg.ac.rs, 0000-0003-3830-2170

Abstract: *Microservice software architecture represents one possible approach for designing complex software products. In industry, microservices have been identified as a common architecture solution, especially when all user requirements, or final product functionalities, are not known or not possible to be defined before the project implementation starts. In software development, source code organization can be structured using a monorepository model, a multirepository model, or a hybrid model, which integrates characteristics of both approaches. This paper presents the advantages and disadvantages of these approaches, provides a definition of microservices, and proposes a model for organizing source code repositories based on these approaches. Model in this research consists of variables that measure the characteristics of software quality, incorporated from ISO 25010 and ISO 25023. Through multiple criteria decision-making, it is possible to choose the alternative that best suits the software system whose development is being carried out. At the very end, final model will be presented with pros and cons of designed model and further research directions using it.*

Keywords: *Mono repository, Multi-repository, Microservices, Source code management, Multiple criteria decision-making.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the development process of complex applications that solve real business problems, it is necessary to establish a correct software architecture model of such software. According to the Larman software development method (Larman, 2005), the first phase is to gather user requirements. Regardless of whether the software development life cycle (SDLC) model is waterfall, or iterative-incremental, the next phase – analysis – should occur if and only if the previous phase has been performed correctly (for the entire software or its current iteration, respectively). After the analysis is completed, and based on its results – including the system structure (conceptual and relational models) and the system behavior (sequence diagrams and defined system operations) – the subsequent development of the software product can proceed in a well-founded manner (Larman, 2005). From the system structure and behavior, software architect can design correct architecture for user interface, application logic, database broker, and other components. Software architect decides on the architecture of the complete software solution, so that it contributes to the simplicity of creating and maintaining the final product, but also makes it easier for the end user. This conceptual solution is the key for minimization, and ideally for prevention, the possibilities of errors on the client side. Due to the increasing complexity of end-user needs, but also the corporate desire to increase the portfolio of companies (both software and from other industries - retail, tourism, etc.), it is necessary to ensure the scalability and maintainability of the software product we are working on.

To ensure the adequate way for realization of the outputs from development phase, architect needs to choose the correct way for source code management. In the near past, adequate ways have been developed for the implementation of various conceptual solutions of software architecture, and especially VCS (Version Control Systems) - mono and multi-repository, which facilitate the manipulation of the entire source code, its versions, and changes by an unlimited number of development teams. During the early 2010s, the concept of microservices emerged, which further facilitates the programming of complex software solutions, where functionalities are implemented through separate units. This type of architecture enables development of each microservice completely or partially separate from another one, and has positive impact on development process of non-waterfall SDLC models.

This paper is organized in five sections. After this introduction, the second section will provide definitions, characteristics, and applications related to key concepts. Third section will provide the mathematical model, with adequate definitions of used characteristics and derived equations. Additionally, third section also provides a problem statement for microservices-based software. Fourth section is posed as a dilemma and discussion for one software architect about implementing one of the four source code management models (SCMs)(i.e. mono and multi repository, hybrid mono-as-multi and hybrid multi-as-mono). The dilemma will be examined in the context of the multi-criteria decision making model. Finally, the conclusions and further research directions are presented in Section 5.

2. BACKGROUND

This part of the paper will explain the concepts, characteristics and applications of mono and multi repositories, but also a hybrid approach that represents a combination of the two mentioned above. In addition, the microservice software architecture will be presented, which completes the theoretical foundations in this section.

Before we begin to analyze the concepts of mono and multi-repository, we must know that there are similarities between them: (1) both models ultimately track the same source code files, and do it by using SCM VCS platforms, such as Git or Mercurial; (2) both models are proven successful for projects of all sizes and (3) both models are straightforward to implement using any typical SCM VCS, up to a scaling limit (Henderson, 2019). However, when considering the dilemma at the level of complex projects, which have hundreds of commits and tens of thousands of code files in their codebase, we come to the point where we need to carefully choose one of them in order to make the solution more readable and functional for the software architects and software developers involved in the project.

2.1. Mono repository

Mono repository (shortened as *monorepo*, or *single repository*) is a type of source control approach where all the components and units of source code are kept in one repository (Shakikhanli & Bilicki, 2022). The main positive characteristics of monorepo projects are: (1) well-organized hierarchical structure, (2) ease of code reuse, (3) simplified dependency management, (4) atomic commits, (5) large-scale code refactoring and (6) collaboration across teams (Potvin & Levenberg, 2016). On the other side, problems that can be caused by complexity and size of monolithic code base are: (1) tooling investments for both development and execution, (2) codebase complexity – including unnecessary dependencies and difficulties with code discovery and (3) effort invested in code health (Potvin & Levenberg, 2016). Intuitively, those disadvantages are implications of mandatory trade-offs, and they need to be well-handled, or the whole product may not be properly driven. The most famous companies that use monorepo approach are: Google, Meta, Microsoft, Uber and Twitter (Brousse, 2019). In practical work, monorepos may seem inflexible to engineers accustomed to having more autonomy over the tools and dependencies they use in their projects (Jaspan et al., 2018).

2.2. Multi repository

Multi-repository, or *Poly-repository* (shortened as *multirepo* or *polyrepo*) approach manages all the packages and source code components in several repositories (Shakikhanli & Bilicki, 2022). Multirepo approach offers benefits from using it, such as: (1) better security than monorepo, (2) more feasible and manageable scalability from the beginning, (3) almost instantaneous versioning, (4) easier ownership assigning, (5) better resource distribution, easier migrating than in monorepo, and (6) easier CI/CD, because of basic separation, which makes it easier to facilitate resources (Plaza, 2023). Worldwide companies that use multi-repo approach for their software are Netflix, Amazon, and Lyft, among the others. Engineers note at least two benefits of multi-repo codebases: ability to maintain stable, versioned dependencies. and the freedom and flexibility to select their own toolchain (Jaspan et al., 2018).

2.3. Hybrid approach

Hybrid approach tries to combine best characteristics of the both models from above, but it needs to stand on one of those mainly, and with another one as the “modification tool” for the first. Because of that, there are two hybrid models: hybrid Multi-as-Mono and hybrid Mono-as-Multi approach. This kind of approach can be suitable in multiple situations. First of all, we can decide the best way to deal with codebase is to have more than one repository, and to use tool like Meta (Walters, 2021) to manage

them. There, we can execute commands against one, all or specific repositories, simply listing them or using some type of condition(e.g. name or logical). This approach is named as Multi-as-Mono. On the other side, Mono-as-Multi approach separates concerns: during development, code is managed like a monorepo, while for deployment, each library's code is copied into its own independent repository. This strategy is prevalent within the PHP ecosystem because Packagist (the main Composer repository) requires a public repository URL to publish a package, and it's not possible to indicate that the package is located within a subdirectory of the repository (Losoviz, 2021).

2.4. Microservices architecture

Microservices are an architectural and organizational approach to software development in which the software consists of several independent services that communicate with each other (AWS, 2024). Such services make applications easier to develop, accelerate innovation, and reduce the time required for deployment (AWS, 2024). Microservice is an independent unit of work, which is small enough to stand on its own in terms of functions.

That means there must be zero coordination for the deployment with other microservices. From this, we can see microservices work on componentized model – a component is a unit of software that is independently replaceable and upgradeable (Bakshi, 2017). Toleration of the each service failure must be integrated in microservice design, and this is one of the crucial differences from monolithic architecture. Services can fail at any time, therefore, it is important to detect failures quickly and automatically restore service. This is why microservice applications put a lot of emphasis on real-time monitoring of the application, checking both architectural elements (such as how many requests per second is the database receiving) and business relevant metrics (such as how many orders per minute are received) (Bakshi, 2017).

The most important principles that a structure should follow to be called a microservice are: separation of concerns, clear boundaries, portability, its own database, temporality, discoverability, and fault tolerance (Frye, 2023). Microservice architecture is based on: loose coupling, security, service registry, single sign-on, transactions, and communication (Redis, 2023). When it comes to implementation, this kind of architecture does not need the existence of full requirement specification at the beginning of project.

3. MODELING AND CRITERIA FOR DECISION-MAKING

This section will present the model and corresponding problem. They are presented through two subsections. First subsection is proposed for problem statement. The main model and variables within it are presented in second subsection. Additionally, in the second subsection we give the explanation of deriving mathematical model and criteria used.

3.1. Problem statement

A software company is developing a complex enterprise system intended for use in a large-scale organizational environment. The system is based on a microservice software architecture and is designed to support a wide range of business functionalities. These include standard data management operations (such as create, read, update, and delete) for various business entities, as well as support for managing their associated properties and relationships. All of this functionalities are arranged as microservices, to ensure autonomous developing and existence of one concrete functionality in case of deleting or changing the other ones. In decision-making time, the decision-maker (software architect) needs to find the best alternative for software product among the defined scope: mono-repository, multi-repository, hybrid mono-as-multi and hybrid multi-as-mono repository. The top management of software company is open for changing the SCM, but requests a brief explanation of the final solution, based on criteria officially used(i.e. standardized criteria).

3.2. Model and variables

Every multi-criteria decision model needs to have sets of alternatives (A) and criteria (C) (Čupić & Suknović, 2010). We will define them as vectors. First vector A is scope of available alternatives, where a_1 represents mono-repository, a_2 represents multi-repository, h_1 represents hybrid mono-as-multi, and h_2 represents hybrid multi-as-mono approach. Then, the alternatives vector A for our case looks like: $A = [a_1, a_2, h_1, h_2]$. Criteria vectors are scopes of software quality metrics. According to ISO 25010 (ISO/IEC, 2011), the nine quality characteristics of software product are: functional suitability, performance efficiency, compatibility, interaction capability, reliability, security, maintainability, flexibility and safety. Each of them

has their own sub-characteristics, and their utilization can be complete or partial, depending on goal which using stands for. Depending on use-case (currently, on purpose of the final software product), all or few of those characteristics can be used for quality evaluation. In the context of repository model selection, we will use sub-characteristics from the performance efficiency subsection of this standard. ISO 25010 describes Time behavior as a degree to which the response time and throughput rates of a product or system, when performing its functions, meet requirements (ISO/IEC, 2011). In same standard, Resource utilization is defined as a degree to which the amounts and types of resources used by a product or system, when performing its functions, meet requirements (ISO/IEC, 2011). Third sub-characteristic, Capacity, is degree to which the maximum limits of a product or system parameter meet requirements (ISO/IEC, 2011). The selected sub-characteristics and relevant software metrics are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Sub-characteristics and software metrics related to Performance quality characteristic (adapted from ISO 25010 standard) (Karnouskos et al., 2018).

Criteria vectors for C_1 , C_2 and C_3 , are the scopes of relevant metrics for evaluating overall validity for Time behavior, Resource utilization and Capacity (Figure 1), respectively. If we generalize these vectors, let $k \in \{1,2,3\}$ denote the index of each strategy vector, and let m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n represent the set of metrics corresponding to each quality criterion, where n is the total number of metrics presented in Figure 1. Then, the general form of each vector can be defined as $C_k = [m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n]$.

Similarly, the general form of the matrix, where columns represent the repository strategy alternatives and rows correspond to the metrics m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n , can be expressed as $O_k = [v_{ij}]$, where v_{ij} is value of metric i for alternative j . Then, there are three matrices in this case, for every sub-characteristic (see Figure 1). Values from matrices O_k follow the rule $v_{ij} \geq 0$, because every metric is non-negative value.

After forming criteria vectors, we need to normalize values to adequate scope, preferable from 0 to 1. A common normalization method is the MAXMIN approach, as shown in equation (1).

$$v_{ij}^{norm} = \frac{v_{ij} - \min(v_i)}{\max(v_i) - \min(v_i)} \quad (1)$$

However, when dealing with metrics where lower values are required (e.g., response time, turnaround time), the MAXMIN strategy must be adjusted. In such cases, we apply an inverted MAXMIN normalization, as defined in equation (2).

$$v_{ij}^{norm} = \frac{\max(v_i) - v_{ij}}{\max(v_i) - \min(v_i)} \quad (2)$$

After this normalization, matrices O_k are transformed(normalized) into matrices O_k^{norm} . The next step is calculation of scores for every column(alternative), for each matrix(criteria scope), which is presented in equation (3). Summary of every criteria scope is vector of same number of elements as the number of alternatives.

$$C_i^{norm} = \sum_{j=1}^3 v_{ij}^{norm} \quad (3)$$

Following this rule, we will have three vectors with four elements each, C_1^{norm} , C_2^{norm} and C_3^{norm} . Those vectors are forming the final matrix F or F_w . In this step, we can introduce weights or not. If we prefer to introduce them, every value for each vector needs to be multiplied by correlated weight coefficient, following

with rule that summary of all weights needs to be equal to 1. Following all of those rules, the general form of the final weighted matrix F_w (or just final matrix F , if we decide for $w_i = 1$) can be expressed as $F_w = [w_i * v_{ij}^{norm}]$.

4. DILEMMA AND DISCUSSION

Evaluation of the mentioned metrics through the presented model is possible in two ways. The first is certainly more difficult - developing appropriate applications for each of the alternatives listed, and measuring and finally comparing metrics through the model. The first way is also the way for solving case study. In that sense, final solution needs to have the best scores of mentioned characteristics, and to manage source code to enable the fastest and safest way for its functionalities. Another way can be an isolated test, similar to beta versions, where a balance is achieved with sufficient abstraction - omitting complexity to the point where the abstracted model still realistically depicts the original product, but also including all the details related to the Performance efficiency components: Time behavior, Resource utilization and Capacity. Let's note that there are a large number of variables in the defined model, so the sensitivity of such a model is the primary challenge in this investigation. Examining a total of 12 listed metrics, there is a possibility of "making up" the results, in the sense that the superiority of one or more metrics in relation to the others "corrects" their simultaneous inferiority in terms of quantitative assessment. This situation is not impossible, especially if we consider the simultaneous presence of metrics related to capacity, which refer to the static capabilities of the system, and on the other hand, the presence of metrics related to Time behavior and Resource utilization, which relate to dynamic capabilities. Then too much positive deviation of some metrics can compensate for the lack of others. It should also be borne in mind that this case, although it has meaning and the possibility of realization in practice, still represents an extreme - borderline possibility. The model's response to this possibility is precisely the weighting coefficients that should be added to equation (3), in order not to give importance to that subgroup of metrics that are more relevant to the software product we are developing. In cases that are not borderline, the model provides clarification between four alternatives, ranking them in order of importance and combining the real performance of the system as recorded by tests and the assessment of the decision maker. The model incorporates expertise from the software architect. The decision maker can, using the explained model, determine the weights w_i based on his knowledge and the specific properties of the software system. The assignment of weights depends on: (1) the industry for which the software is developed; (2) the desire of the end user or the need emphasized by the end user during the definition of requirements; and (3) expertise-based evaluation of team members, mid-level management or other employees in the hierarchy that, in accordance with the specific corporate culture, have an impact on determining the greater or lesser participation of certain characteristics from subsection 3.2. in the final assessment of the mentioned software quality characteristics.

5. CONCLUSION

The software quality characteristics defined in the ISO 25010 standard and the metrics defined in ISO 25023 can be reformulated into a model that provides the ultimate software quality assessment. In this paper, such a model is simplified by using only metrics related to, a sub-characteristics of Performance efficiency - one of the characteristics defined by the standard. In addition, the model in this research is based on the fact that one person should make a final assessment (judgment) about which alternative (model) is the most acceptable for implementation. According to the existing model, that person must perform tests of the real performance of all alternatives (models) and assign adequate weights to the sub-characteristics based on the factors described at the end of the previous section, or on the basis of some others.

Practical application of this model is directly correlated with the problem statement from 3.1., especially if the model is more detailed. In the "limited" version from this paper, model can contribute to the utilization of software working-time, especially execution time, and hardware resources. The main model limitation is that it doesn't incorporate all characteristics and metrics from the ISO standard itself. Additional metrics (e.g., from the ISO 25010 standard, other standards, or user-defined metrics) and their corresponding weights can be incorporated later as a custom model extension.

Further research can be carried out in three directions. (1) Expansion of the model to all nine attributes defined in ISO 25010. Then the model becomes more complex, which contributes to increasing its sensitivity through the increase of variables, but also comprehensiveness, since then its scope includes all characteristics of software quality that the international standard provides. (2) Inclusion of relevant decision makers, listed in Larman's or some other software development method. Then it becomes a group decision-making model. One must be careful here, because the model acquires the dimension of subjectivity of different decision-

makers, who may differ in expert knowledge, experience, level in the company's hierarchy, or in some other aspect of importance for authority in decision-making. (3) Rounding of the whole picture from the aspect of decision-making theory, where the payoff and/or regret tables are included in the model. They should take into account the quantified values of payoffs and losses for each alternative and, based on that, give the decision maker a complete insight into the financial background of the project. Also, an assessment of the time trade-off and other resources that the decision makers or their superiors consider to be important for the company developing the project is carried out.

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